

European Researchers' Night 2024/25

D4.2 Report on Impact Assessment 2024

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1. Executive Summary	3
2. Introduction	4
2.1 Background of the EU-EMBRACES	4
2.2 Objectives	4
2.3 Expected Impact	5
2.4 Scope and structure of the report	6
3. Methodology	6
3.1 Evaluation Approach: rationale for the assessment methodology	6
3.2 Assessment Tools Developed and Implemented	7
3.3 Ethical principles	16
4. Summary of the activities assessed	18
4.1 Science takes the Streets: build-up activities	18
4.2 European Researchers' Night (ERN)	18
4.3 Meet the Scientists program	19
4.5 Participatory debates	20
4.5 Activities in underserved neighbourhoods	21
Activities and Workshops in Underserved Neighborhoods	22
Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools	22
5. Findings and Results	23
5.1 Build-up activities and European Researchers Night(2024)	23
Build-up events	23
ERN 2024	25
5.2 Researchers at Schools Activities (2024)	31
5.3 Dissemination and communication activities	31
7. Challenge and limitations	32
7.1 Challenges in data collection and analysis	32
7.2 Limitations of the assessment tools and methodology	33
8. Conclusions and Recommendations for the next editions	33
8.1 Summary of key results	33
8.2 Recommendations for 2025 Edition	35
Appendix 1. Impact overview	36
Appendix 2. Copies of Assessment Tools	39
9.1 Build-up event and ERN	39
Build-up events ERN 2024 - Activity Form (Organization)	39
Build-up events & ERN 2024 - Survey (Scientists)	41
ERN 2024 - Activity Form (Organization)	43
ERN 2024 - Satisfaction Survey (Participants)	45

<u>9.2 Meet the Scientists campaign</u>	<u>48</u>
<u>Meet the Scientists - Session Form (Teachers)</u>	<u>48</u>
<u>Meet the Scientists - Survey (Students)</u>	<u>50</u>
<u>Meet the Scientists - Survey (Scientists)</u>	<u>53</u>
<u>9.3 Participatory debates</u>	<u>55</u>
<u>Participatory Debates - Session Form (Organization)</u>	<u>55</u>
<u>Participatory Debates - Survey (Students)</u>	<u>58</u>
<u>Participatory Debates (Scientists)</u>	<u>60</u>
<u>9.4 Social inclusion through science and technology</u>	<u>62</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods - Activity Form (Organizers)</u>	<u>62</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods - Satisfaction Survey (Participants)</u>	<u>65</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods - Survey (Scientists)</u>	<u>67</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools - Session Form (Teachers)</u>	<u>70</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools - Survey (Students)</u>	<u>72</u>
<u>Activities and Workshops in Schools - Survey (Scientists)</u>	<u>74</u>

1. | Executive Summary

This report assesses the impact of the **EU-EMBRACES** project in 2024, which aimed to foster public engagement in science, promote inclusivity, and bridge socio-economic gaps in accessing scientific knowledge. The evaluation focuses on outreach activities, audience engagement, and researcher participation, using a combination of surveys, reports, and observational data.

This is an **interim project report** and does not include all collected data, only those related to campaigns completed in 2024. A **full impact assessment will be included in the final report**.

A total of **111 events** were organized, including **32 build-up events, 9 European Researchers' Night (ERN) events, 57 Meet the Scientists sessions, 1 participatory debate,** and **12 Social Inclusion through Science and Technology** activities, engaging **over 35,700 participants**. Notably, **21% of surveyed participants** had their first direct interaction with a scientist, reflecting the project's success in reaching new audiences. Additionally, **835 researchers** contributed to the initiative, with **11% having no prior public engagement experience**.

Efforts to reach underserved communities were a key priority, with **12 activities specifically targeting underserved neighborhoods and TEIP** (Territórios Educativos de Intervenção Prioritária/Educational Territories of Priority Intervention) **schools with historically high dropout rates and retention challenges**, contributing to the project's broader inclusivity goals. In total, **3,410 students** aged 6 to 17 participated in initiatives designed to enhance access to science education, including programs in schools with socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds.

The impact assessment revealed high satisfaction levels with the activities, with **60% of respondents giving the highest rating** and no negative feedback.

Data collection efforts were strengthened through a centralized approach across multiple venues, but challenges remain in increasing researcher survey participation, particularly at large-scale events.

Overall, the results indicate that the project is successfully meeting its intended objectives, aligning with its goals to enhance science communication, engage diverse audiences, and involve researchers in outreach activities.

For future editions, the report recommends maintaining the current assessment framework. Additionally, enhancing researcher engagement in the assessment

through on-site survey collection and potential incentives could improve data accuracy and further enhance the project's impact.

2. | Introduction

2.1 Background of the EU-EMBRACES

The EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools) project, funded by Horizon Europe, is a 20-month initiative running during the biennium 2024-2025. It aims to foster engagement and inclusivity in science communication, focusing on addressing socio-economic inequalities in access to science and innovation. By actively engaging communities that do not typically participate in science communication activities, as well as underrepresented groups, particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, EU-EMBRACES seeks to demonstrate the positive impact of Horizon Europe Missions on everyday lives.

In addition to two editions of the European Researchers' Night (ERN), the project plans to organize a range of activities, including meetings with researchers in schools, participatory debates for students focused on the themes of European Missions, outreach initiatives in underserved neighborhoods, and other public space activities aimed at building excitement in the lead-up to ERN.

Currently in its ninth month, EU-EMBRACES has already organized one edition of the ERN across nine venues in Portugal, and delivered over 80 activities in schools and public spaces, spanning cities, villages, and rural areas across the country.

2.2 Objectives

The main objectives of the EU-EMBRACES project are designed to create a lasting change in the way science is communicated and how underrepresented groups engage with it. These objectives serve as the foundation for measuring the project's success in fostering inclusivity and public engagement.

The six key objectives are:

1. **Increase awareness of science and scientific careers;**
2. **Reach new audiences and underserved communities;**
3. **Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities;**
4. **Involve scientists in science communication activities;**

5. **Showcase EU-funded projects and Portuguese research institutions;**
6. **Organize high-quality outreach activities.**

2.3 Expected Impact

By achieving its objectives, the project aims to generate both **short-term** and **long-term impacts**.

Short-term impacts include:

- Over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.
- Creation of a Youth Ambassadors network of at least 40 students across the country to foster youth involvement and competences in science communication.
- Widespread citizen participation across the country in science outreach activities.
- Active involvement of researchers from diverse scientific fields in public outreach.
- Increased visibility of EU Missions and EU-funded research projects.
- Greater visibility for research institutions and their work.

Mid-term impacts focus on a shift in engagement patterns and attitudes:

- Increased engagement with science among the general population, particularly targeting underserved groups such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations.
- Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future academic and research careers.
- Enhanced communication skills for researchers, allowing them to connect better with non-expert audiences and gaining insights into public concerns.
- Research centers and universities recognizing the importance of outreach beyond traditional audiences and considering new strategies to reach underserved groups.

Long-term impacts aim to produce societal, scientific, and economic changes:

- A more open and inclusive society where meaningful conversations can occur between researchers and citizens, fostering trust in science and the consideration of public perspectives in scientific discourse.
- Empowerment of future generations, equipped with critical and scientific thinking skills, to drive forward innovation and scientific inquiry.
- Promotion of open science, allowing research to be shared with the public and other stakeholders (e.g., industry, policymakers), encouraging the use of scientific results.
- Enhanced job opportunities and career paths in STEM fields for underserved groups, as well as fostering innovation to address societal challenges (e.g., climate change, cancer, sustainability).

These objectives and impacts are being evaluated through key indicators and ongoing assessments throughout its duration.

2.4 Scope and structure of the report

This report presents the methodology used to assess the impact of the EU-EMBRACES project, focusing on data collection, evaluation tools, and key findings from the first nine months, particularly regarding public engagement, researcher involvement, and communication efforts.

The report is structured as follows: Section 3 details the assessment methodology and tools, including ethical considerations. Section 4 summarizes the activities evaluated, categorized by type. Section 5 presents key findings and results from the first nine months of the project. Section 7 discusses challenges and limitations in data collection and impact measurement. Finally, Section 8 provides conclusions and recommendations for future editions, followed by appendices containing assessment tools used in the evaluation.

This is an interim project report and will be complemented by the final impact assessment report at the end of the project, which will provide a comprehensive evaluation, including all planned activities.

3. | Methodology

3.1 Evaluation Approach: rationale for the assessment methodology

Within the overarching framework of fostering engagement and inclusivity in science communication, the six key objectives can be grouped according to their primary focus: three objectives emphasize the **public's involvement** in science through participation in science communication events (Objectives 1, 2, and 3); one objective highlights the active involvement of **researchers** in these events (Objective 4); another centers on enhancing the visibility of **research, EU policies** (missions), and **EU-funded projects** (Objective 5). Finally, the last objective pertains to ensuring the delivery of **high-quality outreach** activities (Objective 6).

In line with these priorities, the impact assessment methodology targets three key stakeholder groups: **event participants, researchers, and event organizers**. It aims to characterize the events, the participating audiences, and the involved researchers while evaluating the impact of these activities both on the public and on the researchers themselves.

Impact, even in the short term, goes beyond what can be captured by surveys and reports. The mere occurrence of an event is, in itself, a measure of impact—even when gathering the perspectives of those involved is not possible. In such cases, indirect evidence, such as photos or personal testimonies, can be used.

Moreover, communication and dissemination activities represent a fundamental dimension of the project's impact. These include outreach campaigns, media coverage, social media engagement, and the ability to generate interest and participation across diverse audiences. Evaluating the effectiveness of these activities helps understanding how well the project reached its objectives and generated impacts.

For this reason, beyond the specific tools developed for this purpose, the assessment also includes data referring to the **organization of the events** and the **communication campaigns** carried out.

Finally, we are fully aware that certain impacts, especially those of a long-term nature, are inherently difficult to measure and evaluate.

3.2 Assessment Tools Developed and Implemented

To characterize the events, the participating audiences, and the involved researchers, while also evaluating the impact of these activities on both the public and the researchers, we established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and corresponding questions specifically tailored to the three stakeholder groups. We then developed a suite of tools to collect both qualitative and quantitative data. These tools included **surveys** (both paper-based and online) directed at participating members of the public and researchers; **voting walls**, such as dot-mocracy and post-it walls, or **show-of-hands voting** aimed at participants; **short reports** completed by event organizers, which also included collected **testimonies** and **photographs**.

The table below outlines each objective of the project alongside its corresponding impacts, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined to evaluate those impacts, and the sources or additional tools selected to assess each KPI.

The table below outlines each objective of the project, along with its corresponding impacts, which are categorized into short-term and mid-term outcomes. It also details the KPIs defined to evaluate these impacts, and the sources or additional tools selected for assessing each KPI. Given that the project is still ongoing, the long-term impacts—related to societal, scientific, and economic changes—are not yet assessable and may be inherently difficult to measure. For this reason, they are not included in the table.

Table 1 - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and information sources used to assess the impact of each project objective

Objective	Impact	KPI	KPI Source & additional insight
1. Increase awareness of science and scientific careers;	Short- term: Over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert	# of events organized # of actions specifically with young people # of participants	Reports from organizers Survey to participants: - <i>What surprised me the most was</i>

	<p>audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.</p>	<p>in the activities % of young participants in ERN</p>	<p>that...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>I didn't know and now I know that...</i> - <i>What do you consider the greatest challenge in science today?</i> <p>Post-it walls:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Three words you associate with science.</i> - <i>What do you consider the greatest challenge in science today?</i> - <i>In your daily life, where do you encounter science?</i> - <i>What is your main source of scientific information?</i> <p>Dotmocracy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Scientists strive to inform society about new discoveries. (Yes, somewhat, no)</i> - <i>Scientific research is influenced by cultural and social factors. (Yes, I don't</i>
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			<i>know, no)</i>
	<p>Mid-term:</p> <p>Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future academic and research careers.</p>	<p>#of events within Meet the Scientist campaign</p> <p># of students involved</p>	<p>Reports from teachers</p> <p>Informations from partners</p> <p>Survey to students:</p> <p>- <i>Do you think you could become a scientist?</i></p> <p>- <i>I didn't know, but in this session, I learned...</i></p> <p>- <i>Was there anything that surprised you during this interaction? What was it?</i></p>
<p>2. Reach new audiences and underserved communities;</p>	<p>Short term:</p> <p>Over 250 activities and events that engage both researchers and non-expert audiences, particularly young people and underserved groups.</p>	<p>Geographical distribution of events across the country</p> <p># of participants in the activities</p> <p>% of public that contacted with scientists for the first time</p> <p>characterization</p>	<p>Reports from organizers</p> <p>Survey to participants (ERN, Researchers at Schools):</p> <p>Characterization of the public (<i>age, gender, postal code, Level of education; professional</i></p>

	<p>Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;</p>	<p>of new publics #of actions specifically with students;</p>	<p><i>status; mother's level of education)</i></p>
	<p>Mid term: Increased engagement with science among the general population, particularly targeting underserved groups such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations</p> <p>Broader participation in science outreach activities of students who may see science as more approachable, opening pathways for future academic and research careers.</p>	<p># of students involved</p> <p># of students that contacted with scientists for the first time</p> <p>#of action specifically with underserved audiences;</p> <p># of activities in unserved neighborhoods and TEIP schools</p>	<p>- Was this the first time you contacted a scientist directly?</p> <p>- Do you usually participate in science events or festivals?</p> <p>- What is your mother's level of education?</p> <p>- What is your connection to science?</p> <p>Survey to students (Researchers at Schools):</p> <p>Characterization of the students (<i>grade level, school, gender, mother's level of education</i>)</p> <p>- Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?</p> <p>- Do you think you could become a scientist?</p> <p>- Have you participated in</p>

			<p><i>other science-related activities (outside of school)?</i></p> <p><i>Could someone like you become a scientist?</i></p> <p>Report from organizers (activities in underserved the neighborhoods): - <i>Did you receive support from any neighborhood structure or person/entity working in the neighborhood?</i> - <i>Was it important for the success of the event?</i></p>
3. Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities;	Short term: Creation of a Youth Ambassadors network of at least 40 students across the country to foster youth involvement and competences in science communication.	# of youth ambassadors involved in the program # of Ciência Viva club involved	Reports from organizers
	Mid-term:	# of participatory debates	Reports from organizers

	15 participatory debates, involving at least 800 students	organized # of students involved in the debates	Survey to students: <i>- Do you feel that your opinion was important to the conclusions of the debate?</i>
4. Involve scientists in science communication activities;	Short-term: Active involvement of researchers from diverse scientific fields in public outreach.	#of researchers involved diversity of scientific areas involved	Survey to scientists: Characterization of researchers involved (<i>Age, gender, Field of Scientific Activity, Professional Category</i>)
	Mid term: Enhanced communication skills for researchers, allowing them to connect better with non-expert audiences and gaining insights into public concerns.	% of scientists with no prior interaction with the public,	Survey to scientists: <i>- Have you participated in science communication activities like this one (direct interaction with the public) before?</i> <i>- Do you feel that your participation was rewarding for you?</i> <i>- Positive aspects of the activity?</i> <i>- Challenges you encountered?</i>

			<p>- How would you describe the students/non-expert audience you interacted with in this session/event?</p>
	<p>Mid-term: Research centers and universities recognizing the importance of outreach beyond traditional audiences and considering new strategies to reach underserved groups.</p>	<p># of research institution involved</p> <p># of institutions that announced their participation in ERN through media platforms (websites, social media,...)</p> <p>% of scientists that often participate in outreach activities</p>	<p>Information from partners</p> <p>Survey to scientists:</p> <p>- Have you participated in science communication activities like this one (direct interaction with the public) before?</p>
<p>5. Showcase EU-funded projects and Portuguese research institutions;</p>	<p>Short-term: EU Missions highlighted;</p>	<p>% of activities in which EU missions were highlighted</p>	<p>Reports for organizers:</p> <p>- Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable)</p> <p>Dot-mocracy:</p> <p>- Which of the European Commission's missions should receive more funding?</p>

	<p>Short-term: EU funded project highlighted.</p>	<p># of scientist funded by EU projects</p> <p># of participating projects funded by the EU;</p>	<p>Information from partners</p> <p>Dot-mocracy:</p> <p>- I knew that the European Commission funds Portuguese scientific projects. (Agree, Don't agree)</p>
	<p>Short-term: Greater visibility for research institutions and their work.</p>	<p># of institutions involved</p>	<p>Information by organizer</p>
<p>6. Organize high-quality outreach activities.</p>		<p>Satisfaction level</p>	<p>Survey to participants:</p> <p>- Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied).</p> <p>- What did you like the most?</p> <p>- What could be improved?</p> <p>- I didn't know and now I know that...</p> <p>Survey to</p>

			<p>students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied); - What did you like most? - What do you think could be improved? <p>Survey to scientists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From the perspective of your participation, highlight challenges you encountered or aspects that could be improved.
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3.3 Ethical principles

The EU-EMBRACES project adheres to high ethical standards in the design and administration of impact assessment tools. These tools, including surveys targeting participants and scientists, are guided by principles that ensure **voluntary participation, anonymity, confidentiality,** and **transparency regarding the objectives** of the data collection process.

Each survey begins with an explanatory introduction, clearly outlining the voluntary nature of participation, the guarantee of anonymity and confidentiality, and the purpose of the questions. To proceed, participants are required to provide explicit consent, which is the only mandatory question included in the surveys.

For online surveys, platforms such as Google Forms are used to collect responses without storing participants' contact information, ensuring data protection. Additionally, participants are provided with contact details for the project team should they have any questions or require further clarification.

In face-to-face contexts, whether the surveys are completed on paper, tablets, or computers, participants are encouraged to fill out the surveys independently, with support staff available to assist only with technical or procedural difficulties. These staff members, including volunteers, organizers, and educators, are trained to explain the purpose of the survey and to facilitate the process while refraining from influencing responses.

For activities conducted in a school setting, surveys are administered to students beginning from the 7th grade of the third cycle of basic education, which corresponds to students aged 12 years and older.

The primary aim of the surveys is to gather statistical insights about the audience, assess their engagement with science both in and outside educational contexts, and evaluate their satisfaction with the event.

Furthermore, the project follows the **evaluation methodology previously applied in the Horizon 2020 project REGGAE (Researchers for European Green Growth Education)**, which was proposed, managed, and implemented by the same consortium leading EU-EMBRACES. The full data collection protocol was submitted to and approved by the i3S ethics committee, ensuring compliance with rigorous ethical standards.

This approach ensures that the project's impact assessment is both ethically sound and aligned with the values and requirements of Horizon-funded initiatives, promoting transparency and respect for all participants involved.

4. | Summary of the activities assessed

4.1 Science takes the Streets: build-up activities

Build-up events are activities organized in the lead-up to the ERN to build excitement and anticipation. These events are held in diverse locations, including streets, markets, squares, natural parks, gardens, museums, theaters, beaches, schools, associations, and many other venues in cities and villages across the country. The aim is to bring research closer to the public by reaching people where they are, rather than relying on them to attend specific venues. This approach is particularly valuable for engaging groups at risk of social exclusion, such as minorities, migrants, or individuals who typically do not participate in science communication activities.

The impact assessment for each build-up event involves an **online report** completed by the partner responsible for organizing the event, along with a survey directed at the participating researchers.

The fields in the online report focus on describing the activity, characterizing the participants and their contexts, and summarizing the activity's impact on the participants, as well as detailing the scientists involved.

The **survey for researchers** gathers information about their profile, their usual involvement in science communication activities, their impressions of the audience, their satisfaction with their participation, and the positive aspects and challenges they experienced.

The full set of questions for both reports can be found in the appendix.

4.2 European Researchers' Night (ERN)

The ERN stands as the centerpiece event, taking place across nine venues throughout the country. Over the course of eight hours, attendees have the opportunity to engage with, learn about, and even experience firsthand the research happening in the country. They can interact with research institutions, companies, NGOs, associations, and school science clubs, as well as with the scientists, experts, and students who make science possible. In addition, the event provides an opportunity to increase familiarity with the EU's five missions and European research projects being conducted in Portugal. The event offers a wide range of activities, including demonstrations, hands-on experiments, talks, speed-dating with researchers, guided tours, games, performances, exhibitions, and much more, providing something for everyone.

The evaluation of the ERN events is the most complex and includes tools tailored to participants, researchers, and the event's organizing partners.

Attendees are asked to complete a **survey** aimed at characterizing the ERN audience and collecting their perceptions of the event. This survey evaluates the public's profile, satisfaction, and perceived impact of the event. Additionally, dynamic and interactive methods are used to gather insights on participants' perceptions of science and technology, and the EU missions. These include **voting walls**, where participants respond to questions by placing stickers (dotmocracy) or writing answers on post-it notes (post-it walls).

Researchers' perceptions are assessed using a **survey** similar to the one used in build-up events. This survey collects information about their profiles, their typical involvement in science communication activities, their impressions of the audience, their satisfaction with their participation, and the positive aspects and challenges they encountered.

The **organizing partners** submit an **online report** detailing the activities they hosted. This report includes comprehensive information about the event, participant demographics and contexts, an evaluation of the activity's impact on participants, and details about the scientists involved.

The full set of evaluation questions is available in the appendix.

4.3 Meet the Scientists program

The *Meet the Scientist* program organizes interactive sessions, both in schools and online, bringing together researchers and students aged 6 to 17. These events aim to spark curiosity and foster a connection between young audiences and the world of science by discussing research fields and exploring how science can be applied in daily life. The program has a dual purpose: on one hand, to inspire young people, particularly those from underserved or minority backgrounds, to consider pursuing scientific careers, and on the other hand, to provide researchers with an opportunity to engage directly with young audiences, share their research outcomes, and enhance their science communication skills.

The evaluation of the *Meet the Scientist* campaign is carried out through reports and surveys.

Teachers, who attend the sessions as observers, complete an **online report**, providing an external perspective on the activity. The report includes fields to describe the activity and its alignment with EU missions (if applicable), characterize the participating students and the school context, and detail the researchers involved. It also focuses on the interaction between students and researchers and assesses the activity's impact on the students. Teachers may also attach photographs to the report, provided they have obtained the necessary permissions and ensure that no students' faces are visible (e.g., photos taken from behind), and that no student is identifiable.

Students aged 12 and above are invited to complete a **survey** that gathers their profiles, satisfaction levels, and perceptions of the event's impact. This survey also explores their prior experience with researchers and science, providing valuable insights into how the activity shapes their perceptions and interest in science.

Researchers' experiences are assessed through a **survey**, which collects information about their professional profiles, typical engagement in science communication activities, impressions about the students, satisfaction with their participation, and reflections on the positive aspects and challenges they encountered during the event.

The full set of evaluation questions is available in the appendix.

4.5 Participatory debates

Participatory debates are in-person events designed for students aged 12 to 17, focused on raising awareness about the EU Missions and the related research conducted within the country. These debates aim to help young people develop critical thinking and debate skills by engaging with cutting-edge topics, supported by researchers and science mediators. Through these dialogue-driven activities, students gain a deeper understanding of the significance of the EU Missions and their possible role in addressing societal challenges.

The impact assessment of participatory debates is conducted through a combination of tools, including an online report completed by the event's organizing partners, as well as surveys targeted at students and researchers.

The **online report**, completed by the **organizing partners**, documents the activity and its alignment with EU Missions, characterizes the participating students, and highlights any effort made to attract diverse audiences and ensure inclusivity and

heterogeneity. It also profiles the researchers involved and evaluates the overall impact of the activity on the students.

Students are invited to complete a **survey** that captures their profiles, satisfaction with the event, prior experiences with researchers and science, and their perceptions of the event's impact. A key question asks whether they felt their opinions were valued in shaping the conclusions of the debate.

Researchers' experiences are evaluated through a separate **survey**, which gathers information about their professional profiles, prior involvement in science communication activities, impressions of the participating students, satisfaction with their role in the debates, and reflections on the positive aspects and challenges they encountered during the event.

The full set of evaluation questions is available in the appendix.

4.5 Activities in underserved neighbourhoods

The events within the program for *Social Inclusion through Science and Technology* are designed to foster engagement with scientists and promote awareness of research, science, and technology. These events are hosted in neighborhoods with limited access to services and resources, aiming to democratize access to scientific and technological knowledge and encourage active citizenship.

The program primarily targets communities in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts, encompassing diverse demographic groups (age, gender, etc.). Its activities fall into two main categories:

1. **Activities and Workshops in Underserved Neighborhoods** – Open to all audiences, including children, families, adults, seniors, and migrant communities.
2. **Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools** – Specifically tailored for students aged 6–17 attending TEIP schools (Territórios Educativos de Intervenção Prioritária/Educational Territories of Priority Intervention).

TEIP Schools in Portugal are located in socio-culturally disadvantaged areas and operate under a program created by the Portuguese Ministry of Education. The program's objectives include reducing school dropout rates, promoting academic success, and fostering social inclusion through targeted strategies adapted to the specific needs of these communities.

Each type of event uses customized evaluation tools to measure its impact, as outlined below:

Activities and Workshops in Underserved Neighborhoods

Organizers of each event complete an **online report** that provides details about the activity, the participants, and their demographic and contextual characteristics. This report also examines whether any support was received from local structures or individuals in the neighborhood and evaluates how important this support was for the event's success. Additionally, the report summarizes the event's overall impact on participants and includes information about the scientists involved, including whether recruiting them was more challenging compared to other similar initiatives.

Participants are invited to provide feedback whenever possible. **Surveys** are used to collect information about their profiles, satisfaction levels, and perceptions of the activity's impact. When surveys are impractical, **alternative methods** are employed, such as voting walls where participants visually indicate their responses or informal polls answered by raising hands. These methods aim to capture participants' satisfaction, the perceived impact of the event, and their connection to science.

Researchers' experiences are also evaluated through **online surveys**. These gather information about their professional profiles, previous involvement in science communication activities, and their impressions of the event. Scientists are asked about satisfaction with their participation, the positive aspects of the activity, and any challenges or areas for improvement they encountered.

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools

Activities in TEIP schools are evaluated using the same tools applied in the *Meet the Scientist* campaign.

Teachers, attending the sessions as observers, complete an **online report** that provides an external perspective on the activity. The report includes fields to describe the activity, its alignment with EU missions (if applicable), details about the participating students, and the school context. It also highlights the interaction between students and researchers, assesses the activity's impact on the students, and documents details about the researchers involved. Teachers may also submit photographs, provided they have obtained the necessary permissions and ensure student anonymity by avoiding identifiable images (e.g., photos taken from behind).

Students aged 12 and above are invited to complete a **survey** that gathers information about their profiles, satisfaction levels, and perceptions of the event's impact. This survey also explores students' prior exposure to scientists and science, offering valuable insights into how the activity influences their perceptions and interest in science.

Researchers' experiences are assessed through a **survey**, capturing their professional backgrounds, typical engagement in science communication activities, impressions of the students, and reflections on their participation. The survey invites researchers to evaluate the positive aspects of the activity, identify challenges they faced, and suggest areas for improvement.

5. | Findings and Results

5.1 Build-up activities and European Researchers Night(2024)

Build-up events

Sipping hydromel on the beach, while discussing the science of fermentation and learning about citizen science projects focused on antibiotic resistance; encountering an installation with five bicycles on the street, in a square, or outside the school, where participants can pedal to understand how a hydroelectric power plant, a solar power plant, or other clean energy devices work; strolling through a natural park to understand the processes of soil formation in the Limestone Massif of central Portugal and observing the results with their own eyes; visiting a regenerative agriculture farm to discover how food can be grown in ways that benefit both nature and communities, and tasting the products; walking through the corridors of a Cruise Terminal, experiencing scientific and recreational activities focused on the aquatic environment; entering the weekly market to attend storytelling sessions among the market stalls, participating in origami workshops, and joining guided tours and workshops to learn about plants and the research being conducted on the fascinating world of plants; attending a photography exhibition at school showcasing women undergoing cancer treatment, stimulating discussions and raising awareness about therapies while challenging prejudices...

Probably, the greatest impact of the **build-up events** came from bringing science and researchers out of research centers and into streets, squares, public markets,

beaches, theaters, natural parks, municipal offices, museums, and many other public venues across the country.

We organized **32 build-up** events in **25** different places, involving **27,427 participants** and **284 researchers**. These events featured workshops, field trips, BioBlitz activities, science cafés, talks, art therapy workshops, interactive exhibitions, renewable energy simulations, and hands-on activities. Topics covered a wide range of subjects, including regenerative agriculture, cancer awareness, renewable energy, climate change adaptation, geology, archaeology, robotics, and more.

Among these, **3** were specifically targeted at underserved audiences (migrant communities, at-risk youth recovery programs, and socially and economically vulnerable people, in situations of deprivation, exclusion, and risk), and **7** were specifically directed at students. Other audiences included families, senior communities, teachers, and the general public.

Given the diverse nature of the events, most of the **feedback and comments from participants** came from observations made by the organizers or from transcriptions of remarks during conversations and exchanges of opinions stimulated by the events. When changes were identified, they mostly stemmed from comments by individuals who had never previously interacted with researchers or research centers, or those who were surprised by the knowledge of techniques, therapies, or research projects taking place in the local area. In events where surveys were administered, 14% of respondents reported that they had never attended a science event, and 25% claimed they had no connection to science.

In the case of lectures, exhibitions, or walks, many reported comments referred to the level of public engagement.

Although not quantifiable, the 32 events held between May and September 2024 served as valuable opportunities to raise awareness, while also inviting participation in the main **Night Event** of September.

Participants in Build-up events (2024)

Researchers in Build-up events (2024)

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of build-up events in 2024; participants (left) and researchers (right) involved in each event.

ERN 2024

The EU-EMBRACES project organized **9 ERNs in diverse locations**, such as the Oeiras seafront, the i3S research center on the outskirts of Porto, the *Pavilhão do Conhecimento* exhibition center in Lisbon, the planetarium at the Monastery of Tibães (Braga), an old hydroelectric power station located on the left bank of the Fervença River, now home to the Bragança Ciência Viva Center, the museum near the archaeological site of rock art in the Côa and Douro Valleys (Vila Nova de Foz Côa), the Alviela Ciência Viva Center near Portugal's largest karst spring, the Convento das Maltezas which houses the Estremoz Ciência Viva Center, and the Ciência Viva Center of Lagos located in the heart of the city.

These events, attended by anywhere from around 50 to more than 1,500 participants, totaled **4,918 attendees** during the afternoon and evening of September 27th, along with **511 researchers**.

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of ERNs in 2024: number of participants per event (left) and postal codes of participants for each venue (right).

Over **230 activities** took place, including hands-on workshops, exhibitions, science shows, demonstrations, competitions, games, escape rooms, speed dating with researchers, and astronomy observations. There were also virtual guided tours, stand-up comedy, music and dance performances, tastings, and street art, providing a wide range of engaging experiences for participants. **EU Corners** at each venue highlighted EU-funded research and opportunities. Special efforts were made to **engage communities with limited access to science communication**, including musicians and dancers from **underserved neighborhoods**, the **deaf community**, individuals facing **social and economic challenges** such as deprivation, exclusion, and risk, as well as **young students** from vocational high schools specializing in **communication**.

Through the collection of **953 participant surveys**, distributed in paper format to those leaving the venue, we gained valuable insights into our audience. The majority of attendees were young, with **40% under the age of 24**, while **6% were over 65**. Additionally, nearly 80% were evenly split between students and employed individuals, and 60% of respondents identified as female.

One of the most striking findings was that for **20%** of participants, this was their **first-ever encounter with a scientist**. Furthermore, just over 20% reported having no direct connection to science. Notably, among these newcomers, the age distribution

was fairly uniform, indicating that the event successfully engaged a broad demographic.

Figure 3. Demographics of the public in ERNs in 2024 (based on 953 participant surveys): age distribution (top left), gender distribution (bottom left), education level distribution (BE = Basic Education, SE = Superior Education) (top right), and employment status (bottom right).

When asked to rate their overall satisfaction on a scale from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied), more than 60% of respondents awarded the highest rating, while over 30% gave it a 4—demonstrating an overwhelmingly **positive reception**.

We also asked participants what they appreciated most and what could be improved. The most successful activities included:

- **Interactive Experiences:** Human gyroscope, suspended bicycle, and hands-on activities in plant biology and microbiology
- **Workshops:** Coral conservation, nutrition, and sustainable agriculture
- **Exhibitions:** Cancer research and microbiology
- **Science Shows:** with live chemistry experiments
- **Demonstrations:** Food technology, lab-grown food, robotics, hydrogen and electric cars, autonomous FI cars, hydroponics, biomaterials, and artificial organs
- **Informal Talks:** Climate change from historical, geological, and contemporary perspectives

- Games & Virtual Tours:** Escape room game on epidemics and research methods, antibiotic resistance, virtual guided tours undersea conservation, cosmic rays, and boat tours.

Figure 4. Public's Connection with Science and Satisfaction Levels in ERN 2024 (based on 953 participant surveys): Percentage of attendees who had their first contact with researchers during the event (top left), age distribution of those experiencing their first interaction with a scientist (bottom left), attendees' connection to science (categories: No direct connection to science, Friends or family work in science, Trained in a scientific field, Work or have worked in science, Other) (top right), and satisfaction levels of attendees from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied) (bottom right).

In terms of positive feedback, participants particularly appreciated the **variety and diversity of activities**, the wide range of scientific topics, and the tailored sessions designed for different audiences, including children, young people, and adults. The **involvement of multiple institutions and research centers** was also highly valued. Many attendees highlighted the **interactive** nature of the activities and expressed gratitude for the **opportunity to engage directly with scientists**, praising their availability, enthusiasm, clarity, and friendliness.

The event's **vibrant atmosphere** was another key strength. Participants noted the **strong presence of young people—not just among attendees, but also among organizers and researchers**—which contributed to a dynamic and engaging

environment. Many also appreciated the **diversity of the audience**, with students, teachers, parents, and children all participating together.

Regarding **areas for improvement**, some attendees at smaller venues expressed a desire for a greater variety of activities. While this reflects strong audience interest, expanding these offerings is not always feasible due to resource constraints. Additionally, there was a call for broader event promotion. However, given the high attendance levels, many participants instead suggested increasing venue space to accommodate the large crowds and extending the event duration.

Figure 5. Researchers Participating in ERN 2024: Frequency of researchers' participation in science communication activities with direct public engagement (based on 156 online surveys) (left) and geographical distribution of participation, showing the number of researchers involved across the 9 venues (based on reports from organizing partners) (right).

A total of **795 researchers** participated in the build-up events and European Researchers' Night (ERN) 2024. To assess their experience and impact, we collected **156 online survey responses**, representing approximately **20%** of all participating researchers (53 out of 284 involved in build-up events and 102 out of 511 from ERN). Despite the sample size, the data provides valuable insights into the demographics and engagement patterns of participating scientists.

Among the surveyed researchers, **11%** were participating in a public science communication event with direct audience engagement for the first time, while **23%** reported frequent participation, attending **more than five outreach events per year**.

These findings suggest that while ERN and its associated build-up events successfully attract newcomers to science communication, they also serve as a platform for experienced researchers who regularly engage with the public.

High frequency of respondents (37%) were **under 35 years old**, reflecting a trend also observed in the participant surveys. However, researchers from all age groups took part, including 4% aged over 65.

In terms of professional category, the most represented groups were Career researchers and lecturers (42%), followed by PhD students (28%) and Master's students (13%). Finally, 62% of respondents identified as female, which may indicate strong participation from women in public engagement activities but could also be due to a greater willingness of women to respond to surveys, as observed in the literature.

The participating researchers came from diverse scientific disciplines, including biological sciences, physical sciences, exact sciences, social sciences, engineering, medicine, law, and humanities. However, the majority (52%) were from the natural sciences, highlighting a strong presence of researchers in these fields.

Figure 6. Demographic of researchers that participated in ERN 2024 and build-up events (based on 156 online surveys): age distribution (top left), professional career distribution (top right), gender distribution (bottom left), research area (bottom right).

5.2 Researchers at Schools Activities (2024)

Due to the academic calendar, school-based activities—such as the *Meet the Scientists* program and *Participatory Debates*—only commenced in September 2024. As a result, the majority of activities will be concentrated within the 2024/2025 school year.

A total of **57 sessions** (34 of which were held in person) took place in 2024, engaging **3,088 students** aged 6 to 18 and involving **51 scientists**. Assessment data is available for **33 of these sessions**, which collectively involved **1,514 students** (974 of whom were over 12 years old and, therefore, eligible to respond to our surveys) and **36 participating researchers**.

The full impact analysis will be completed by the end of the school year. However, preliminary observations indicate that the percentage of **students** who had direct contact with a scientist for the first time is **higher** compared to participants in the European Researchers' Night (ERN), standing at **27%**, with an additional **12%** of students uncertain whether it was their first time.

Regarding the **researchers** involved in school activities, we observed that **all** participants already had prior experience in direct public engagement. Although these are preliminary results, they suggest that while the ERN and its build-up events serve as an entry point for researchers new to outreach activities, those who engage in school-based initiatives tend to already have prior experience in science communication activities.

In 2024, the project also organized **one participatory debate** involving **22 students and 2 scientists**. A full impact assessment of these debates will be included in the final report.

Additionally, **12 activities** were carried out in disadvantaged neighborhoods, engaging **146 participants** and **14 scientists**, with the goal of democratizing access to scientific knowledge and fostering active citizenship. As of project month 9 (M9), we have collected evaluation data for only **2 of these activities**, conducted in an underserved neighborhood of Lisbon. The complete impact assessment of these initiatives, along with data from events in 2025, will be included in the final report.

5.3 Dissemination and communication activities

The impact evaluation of the ERN project extends beyond the events themselves and beyond the perspectives and impressions of the participants, including the public,

researchers, and event organizers. Specifically, the impact also includes the dissemination of the project and the ERN, along with the related events. Communication and dissemination activities have proven to be a fundamental aspect of the project's overall impact, demonstrating the ability to generate interest and participation from a wide range of audiences.

As outlined in Deliverable D1.2 - Communication Report, the ERN project achieved extensive reach across various media channels, generating significant attention with coverage on over 37 major platforms, including prominent television and online publications. Key media outlets included *Público*, a digital newspaper with over **47,000 paid subscriptions**, and *CMTV*, a television channel with a daily audience of more than **100,000 viewers**.

A promotional video for ERN was aired on *RTP2* and *RTP3 – Rádio e Televisão de Portugal* channels, which together account for **1.7% of the total audience share in Portugal**. Additionally, a **digital advertisement** in *Público* generated over **127,000 impressions**, greatly enhancing the campaign's visibility.

The project's **digital outreach** also had a significant impact, reaching **32,000 users** through social media campaigns, while the ERN website attracted **8,300 visitors**.

7. | Challenge and limitations

7.1 Challenges in data collection and analysis

One of the major challenges faced in data collection is standardizing the process across the various venues within our consortium. The consortium includes diverse venues, ranging from research centers to science centers and museums, each with different resources and located in varied contexts. As a result, these venues host different types of events, which take place in a range of settings, including cities, suburban areas, smaller urban centers, and even some venues located outside urban areas. This diversity complicates efforts to ensure consistency in data collection methods and outcomes.

Another significant challenge has been achieving high response rates from both participants and researchers to our surveys. For this edition, we decided to distribute paper surveys in addition to the online ones at venues where this was feasible. While this approach increased the likelihood of capturing more responses, it also introduced additional costs, such as the need to digitize the paper responses before centralizing the data analysis.

Some venues, such as the one in Oeiras, experimented with offering a token—a NEI-branded tote bag featuring science-related wordplay—as an incentive for survey completion. Although this strategy is not always easy to implement due to the associated costs, it proved to be successful in increasing response rates.

7.2 Limitations of the assessment tools and methodology

While our impact evaluation provides valuable insights, it is important to recognize the limitations inherent in the assessment tools employed, such as surveys, reports, and voting walls. These tools primarily capture immediate impacts, but they are less effective at measuring long-term outcomes. First and foremost, it is important to note, as previously mentioned, that the realization of the events themselves represents an impact in its own right, even if its full effects are not immediately measurable. Regarding long-term outcomes, the gradual familiarization of the public with the ERN initiative, as well as the more subtle effects of public-facing materials like street posters, remain difficult to quantify. Furthermore, certain indirect impacts—such as the deeper engagement or sustained interest generated by the events—are not fully captured by our current methodologies. While the events generate immediate and measurable impact, some broader, longer-term effects may not be adequately reflected in the available data.

8. | Conclusions and Recommendations for the next editions

8.1 Summary of key results

By the end of 2024, the EU-EMBRACES project has successfully advanced its mission to foster engagement and inclusivity in science communication, with a strong focus on reducing socio-economic barriers to accessing science and innovation. The project has made significant progress toward its key objectives.

Below is a summary of the main results for each objective.

Objective 1: Increase awareness of science and scientific careers

- 111 activities organized: 32 build-up events, 9 ERN events, 57 *Meet the Scientists* events, 1 participatory debate, 12 social inclusion events.
- Participants: 35,755 attendees, 40% under 24 years old.
- *Meet the Scientists* program: 71 events, 3,410 students involved.

Figure 7. Geographical distribution of EU-EMBRACES events in 2024, including Build-Up events, ERNs, and Meet the Scientists events. Participant distribution (left) and researchers involved (right).

Objective 2: Reach new audiences and underserved communities

- Participation: 35,755 total participants, 1,569 surveyed.
- First-time Encounters: 21% had their first direct contact with a scientist, 27% of students in *Meet the scientists* activities met a scientist for the first time.
- Student Actions: 72 actions with students, 3,410 students involved.
- Underserved Audiences: 12 activities in underserved neighborhoods/TEIP schools, 19 with underserved audiences.
- Young audience: 43 actions specifically with young people, 40% of participants in ERN were young

Objective 3: Promote public engagement with science, particularly through participatory activities

- Engagement: 154 youth ambassadors, 9 Ciência Viva clubs, 1 participatory debate with 22 students.

Objective 4: Involve scientists in science communication activities

- Researchers Involved: 835 researchers from various scientific fields.
- Scientific Areas: Natural sciences (47%), Medical & Health Sciences (17%), Agricultural Sciences (12%).

- Experience: 11% of scientists had no prior public engagement experience, 59% participate in outreach regularly.

Objective 5: Showcase EU-funded projects

- EU Projects Highlighted: 87 EU research projects, 68 scientific institutions involved.

Objective 6: Organize high-quality outreach activities

- Satisfaction Level: 60% gave the highest rating, no negative feedback.

8.2 Recommendations for 2025 Edition

Overall, the tools used for data collection and impact evaluation in 2024 performed as expected, and we are satisfied with their effectiveness. We do not anticipate any major changes for 2025. The collaboration among venues to centralize data collection was also successful and streamlined the process.

However, one area for improvement is increasing the response rate for surveys directed at researchers, particularly for larger events like certain Build-Up and ERN activities. To address this, we recommend collecting survey responses on the event day itself, rather than postponing the request. Additionally, where feasible, offering small incentives such as branded tokens could help increase participation and improve data quality.

These adjustments would enhance engagement and provide more comprehensive insights into the impact of large-scale events.

Appendix 1. Impact overview

Below is the **Impact Overview Table at Month 9** of the project, outlining its progress and impact so far. It is divided into **short-term** and **mid-term impact**:

- **Foreseen Impact** – Expected outcomes for the project as a whole.
- **State of the Art at M9** – Current progress based on collected data.
- **Additional Information** – Relevant contextual details, if applicable.

Long-term impacts are not included, as they require more time to assess and will be evaluated in later stages.

Table 2 – Impact overview of EU-EMBRACES at month 9

Foreseen Impact (project as a whole)	State of the art at M9	Additional information (if applicable)
Short-term result		
A set of activities and events involving researchers and lay-audiences, in particular young people, and underserved audiences;	32 build-up events; 9 ERN events; 57 meet the scientists events; 1 participatory debate; 12 Social inclusion through science and technology events; 43 actions specifically with young people; 19 actions specifically with underserved audiences;	This count includes 4 activities during the ERN of Oeiras aimed at underserved audiences.
A Youth Ambassadors network;	154 students engaged to lead and animate activities during the NIGHT;	These students, along with others who will participate in the next edition of the ERN, will receive training in science communication

		through specialized workshops.
Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;	Over 35,755 people have participated in EU-Embraces science outreach events by the end of 2024;	Includes build-up events, the main NIGHT events, Meet the scientists campaign, Participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology, and Youth Ambassadors program.
Researchers from all scientific areas engaged in science outreach activities;	<p>835 researchers involved so far from research areas that includes:</p> <p>Natural sciences: 47% Medical and Health Sciences: 17% Agricultural Sciences: 12% Engineering and Technology: 10% Social Sciences: 4% Exact Sciences: 3% Humanities: 2% Environmental Sciences: 1% Interdisciplinary: 1% Pharmaceutical Sciences: 1% Law: 1% Science Communication: 1% Marine Biotechnology: 1% Unknown: 2%</p>	
EU Missions highlighted;	EU missions presented in 66% of the activities;	
Research institutions with more visibility.	68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);	
Mid-term outcomes		

<p>Increase the proportion of the national population engaging with science, particularly among underserved audiences such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations. We anticipate that creating new opportunities for citizens to encounter science will spark greater interest in science-related issues in the future, leading to broader participation in science outreach activities and venues;</p>	<p>Among the 1,569 surveys administered to participants of outreach events, 21% reported that this was their first time having direct contact with a scientist.</p> <p>Focusing exclusively on surveys from participants of the <i>Meet the Scientist</i> activities (out of 616 surveys), this percentage increases to 27%, with an additional 12% stating that they were unsure.</p>	
<p>By involving school students in science, we expect to break barriers they may have in considering research as a potential career, showing that science is not too complicated nor uninteresting. We aim to bring a new cohort of students, specially from minorities and underserved groups, to universities, and later on to scientific and academic careers.</p>	<p>3,410 students involved;</p>	<p>This figure includes only the students who participated in the Researchers at Schools activities by the end of 2024—including the Meet the Scientists campaign, participatory debates, and youth ambassadors.</p> <p>To this number, students who participated in the build-up events and NEI should be added, for which only estimates are available: 760 and 800, respectively.</p>

<p>By involving researchers in different types of science outreach initiatives, we contribute to improving their communication skills and giving them new perspectives on the public's concerns and opinions on their scientific topic.</p>	<p>Number of researchers involved in outreach initiatives: 835</p> <p>11% of researchers known to have participated in outreach activities for the first time</p>	
<p>Research centres and universities realise the importance of participating in science outreach activities that go beyond preaching to the choir and start considering new strategies for reaching underserved audiences.</p>	<p>68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);</p>	<p>A number of institutions proactively reached out to the organizing partners to express their interest in participating in the ERN.</p>

Appendix 2. Copies of Assessment Tools

9.1 Build-up event and ERN

Build-up events ERN 2024 – Activity Form (Organization)

This form is intended to gather information about activities carried out as pre-events for the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form must be completed for each event/activity.

The form should be completed by the organization responsible for the activity, ideally by someone directly involved in its implementation. The form fields refer to the activity, participants, the activity's impact on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan data collection in advance. Please submit the form with the information available, even if it is not possible to fill in all fields.

Filling out the form does not take much time. We thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title** *Required*
 - **Date** *Required* (Month, day, year)
 - **Location** *Required*
 - **Duration**
 - **Type of Activity** *Required*
 - **Organizing Entity**
-

Participants

- **Number of Participants (approximate)** *Required*
 - **Age Range of Participants**
 - **Context(s) of Participants**
(*e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.*)
-

Scientists

- **Number of Scientists Involved** *Required*
 - **Scientific Fields of the Scientists**
-

Impact of the Activity on Participants

- **Participants' Satisfaction with the Activity**
Rate from 1 (Very Dissatisfied) to 5 (Very Satisfied):
- **How was participants' satisfaction assessed?**
 - Observation
 - Surveys
 - Written Comments
 - Oral Comments
 - Dotmocracy

- Post-it Wall
- Other (specify)
- **Was it possible to identify any impact or changes in participants? What changed?**

Examples:

- Participants who had never previously engaged with science spoke with a scientist for the first time.
- Participants learned that becoming a scientist is a possible career path in Portugal.
- Participants discovered previously unknown aspects of science.
- Scientists who had never interacted with the public before gained experience in public engagement.

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

- **Evidence of Change**

Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the identified change. You may also add photographs of the event or other materials showcasing the activity's impact (e.g., dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.).

- **Photographs**

Build-up events & ERN 2024 – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire is intended to evaluate scientists' perceptions of the event. The responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 3 minutes.

Participation is voluntary. You may decline to complete it or abandon it at any time.

Your responses will always remain confidential. They will be submitted to a Google Forms link that only the project researchers can access. Google Forms does not require registration and does not collect identifiable data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify you or know whether you participated in the survey.

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or its procedures, please contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

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ELECTRONIC CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you confirm that:

- You have read the information above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years or older.
 - **I Agree**
 - **I Do Not Agree (Exit Survey)**

The activity

- **Event or Activity Title**
- **Date** (Month, Day, Year)
- **Event Location**
- **Organizing Entity**
- **Did the event take place during the European Researchers' Night?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Age**
 - Under 35
 - 35–44
 - 45–54
 - 55–64
 - Over 65
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
 - Other: [Specify]
- **Scientific Field of Activity**

- Exact Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Other: [Specify]
- **Professional Category / Relationship with Science**
 - Master's Student
 - Ph.D. Student
 - Postdoctoral Researcher (with fellowship or fixed-term contract)
 - Career Researcher or Academic Staff
 - Other: [Specify]
- **Have you participated in science communication activities like this one (direct interaction with the public) before?**
 - No, this was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2–4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate frequently (5 or more times per year)
- **How would you describe the people (non-scientists) you interacted with during this activity?**
- **Do you feel your participation in this activity was rewarding for you? If so, in what way?**
- **From your perspective, what were the positive aspects of this activity?**
- **From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter, or what aspects could be improved?**
- **Additional Comments:**

ERN 2024 – Activity Form (Organization)

This form is intended to gather information about the 2024 and 2025 European Researchers' Night event. A separate form must be filled out for each night.

The responsibility for completing the form lies with the organizing entity of the activity.

The fields in this form refer to the description of the activity, the participants, the scientists involved, and the impact of the activity on the participants. It may be

necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available data, even if not all fields can be completed.

Filling out the form is quick and simple. We thank you in advance for your cooperation.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title**
- **Date**(Month, day, year)
- **Location**
- **Duration**
- **Type of activity**

Participants

- Approximate number of participants
- Age range of participants
- Context(s) of participants
(e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.)

Scientists

- Number of scientists involved
- Scientific areas of the scientists

Impact of the activity on participants

- Participant satisfaction with the activity (if applicable)
Where 1 means very dissatisfied and 5 means very satisfied
- How was participant satisfaction measured?
 - Observation

- Surveys
- Written comments
- Oral comments
- Dotmocracy
- Post-it wall
- Other...
- Was any impact or change identified in the participants? What changed?
For example:

There were participants who had never had prior contact with science, who spoke with a scientist for the first time, who were unaware that being a scientist was a possible career in Portugal, or who were unaware of certain aspects of science.

There were scientists who had never interacted with the public before...

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

Evidence of change

Include comments, testimonies, or observations that demonstrate the change.

You may also add photographs of the event or others that show the impact of the activity (dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.).

Photographs

ERN 2024 – Satisfaction Survey (Participants)

The following questions aim to assess your perception of this event and help us characterize the audience that joined us for this European Researchers' Night using statistical indicators.

The answers are personal, please respond based on your own experience. Completing this survey should not take more than 5 minutes. Participation is voluntary, and you can refuse to answer or exit the survey at any point. Your responses will be extremely useful in improving your experience, as well as that of other participants, in future activities. We guarantee that your answers will always remain confidential.

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European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact: If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or the procedures, you can contact us via sci@itqb.unl.pt.

Consent: By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are participating voluntarily.

I agree

I do not agree

Location of the ERN

Where did the European Researchers' Night you are referring to take place?

- CCV Alcalena
- CCV Braga
- CCV Bragança
- CCV Estremoz
- CCV Lagos
- CCV Lisboa
- CCV Vila Nova de Foz Côa
- Oeiras
- Porto

Share your impressions with us!

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
- **What did you like the most?**
- **What could be improved?**
- **I didn't know and I found out that...**

Now, help us get to know the audience who joined us at this event by providing some information about yourself.

- **Age**
 - Under 15 years
 - 15-24 years

- 25-34 years
- 35-44 years
- 45-54 years
- 55-64 years
- 65 years or older
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other
- **Postal Code** (if you reside outside Portugal, you can indicate the country)
- **Level of education**
 - Primary education - 1st cycle
 - Primary education - 2nd cycle
 - Primary education - 3rd cycle
 - Secondary education
 - Post-secondary education
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - PhD
 - Other
- **Professional status**
 - Student
 - Employed
 - Unemployed
 - Homemaker
 - Retired
 - Other
- **Mother's level of education**
 - No schooling
 - Primary education
 - Secondary education
 - Higher education
 - Other.
- **Was this the first time you interacted with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **Do you usually participate in science events or festivals?**
 - Never participated before

- Yes, occasionally
- Yes, frequently
- **What is your connection to science?**
 - I have no direct connection to science
 - I have friends or family who are scientists
 - I have training in a scientific area
 - I work or have worked in science
 - Other

9.2 Meet the Scientists campaign

Meet the Scientists – Session Form (Teachers)

This form is designed to collect information about the Meet the Scientist sessions within the framework of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be filled out for each session.

The form should be completed by the teacher who attended the session. The fields in the form relate to the activity, the scientists, the participants, and the effect of the activity on the participants. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if not all fields can be completed.

The completion of the form does not take much time. We appreciate your collaboration in advance.

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Format

- Online
- In-person

If the session was in-person, please indicate the location where it took place:

Session Theme

- Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable):
 - Beating Cancer
 - Tackling Climate Change
 - Developing the Cities of the Future
 - Ensuring Soil and Food Health
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable

Duration of the session**Session Description**

Please briefly describe what the session consisted of, including the socioeconomic context of the school and the habits of interaction (or lack thereof) with scientists.

Describe the conditions that influenced the interaction, facilitating or hindering it. (If the meeting was in-person, detail the location, available space, and materials used, such as computers or laboratory equipment. If it was online, comment on the participation dynamics, tools used, and relevant logistical aspects.)

Participants**Number of students (approximate)****Educational level**

- Primary Education (1st cycle)
- Primary Education (2nd cycle)
- Primary Education (3rd cycle)
- Secondary Education
- Other

Scientists**Number of scientists involved****Scientific area of the scientist(s)**

Please rate the following statements according to your level of agreement (agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, not applicable):

- The scientist(s) adapted their speech to the age/knowledge of the students.
- The scientist(s) sought to promote the participation of the students.
- The scientist(s) showed interest in the students' questions/opinions.

Effect of the session on the participants

During the session, the students were:

- Bored
- Distracted
- Attentive
- Enthusiastic
- Participative
- Other...

Was it possible to identify any impact/change in the participants? What changed?

For example: did students talk to a scientist for the first time, learn something new, discover a scientific career, or form an opinion on a new topic?

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

Evidence(s) of change

Include here any comments, testimonies, or observations that demonstrate the change observed.

You can also add photographs from the event or others that highlight the impact of the activity.

Note: If you wish to include photographs, make sure to ask for permission to take pictures, ensure that no faces are visible (photograph from behind), and that no student is identifiable.

Other observations/comments that can help us assess the impact of the session on participants (and scientists)

Photographs

Meet the Scientists - Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us characterize the audience who participated in this event using statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to answer or leave the survey at

any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the questionnaire will take no more than 5 minutes, and your contributions will be extremely valuable for improving both your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely the responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact.

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

Consent.

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are voluntarily participating.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Share your impressions of this session with us.

Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied):

What did you like most?

What do you think could be improved?

I didn't know, but in this session, I learned...

Help us better understand the audience that joined this event through statistical indicators.

Grade level

- 7th grade
- 8th grade

- 9th grade
- 10th grade
- 11th grade
- 12th grade

School

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other...

Your mother's education level

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education
- Other...

Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Was there anything that surprised you during this interaction? What was it?

Do you think you could become a scientist?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside of school)?

- No, never
- Yes, occasionally
- Yes, regularly

Meet the Scientists – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to assess the perception of scientists about the "Meet the Scientist" event within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project.

The responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this questionnaire is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or discontinue at any point.

Your responses will always remain confidential.

The responses will be sent to a Google Forms link, which only project researchers can access. Google Forms does not require registration or collect identifying data, such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or procedures, you can contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

ELECTRONIC CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years of age or older.

I Agree

I Do Not Agree (leave survey)

Age

- Under 35
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- Over 65

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other...

Field of Scientific Activity

- Exact Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Other...

Professional Category

- Master's Student
- PhD Student
- Doctoral Researcher with a fellowship or fixed-term contract
- Career Researcher or Professor
- Other...

Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct contact with the public)?

- No, this was my first time
- Yes, I participate occasionally
- Yes, I participate regularly (2-4 times per year)
- Yes, I participate regularly (5 or more times per year)

Type of participation in the session:

- Online
- In-person

How would you describe the students you interacted with in this session?

Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If so, how?

From your perspective, what positive aspects would you highlight?

From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter or aspects that could be improved?

Other observations/comments

9.3 Participatory debates

Participatory Debates – Session Form (Organization)

This form is designed to collect information about the debates organized as part of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be filled out for each session.

The form should be completed by the organization responsible for the activity, ideally by the main facilitator of the debate or someone who was present during the session. The fields cover information about the activity, participants, the effect of the activity on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan in advance to gather the required information. Please submit the form with the available information, even if not all fields can be completed.

Completing this form is quick and straightforward. Thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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- **Session Date** (Month, day, year)
 - **Location**
 - **Session Topic**
 - **Horizon Europe Mission covered during the session (if applicable):**
 - Beating Cancer
 - Fighting Climate Change
 - Developing Future Cities
 - Ensuring Soil Health and Food Security
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable
 - **Duration**
 - **Brief Description of the Session**
(Include information such as the social context of the school, room conditions that might facilitate or hinder participation, presence of teachers, and any other relevant aspects...)
-

Participants

- **Number of Students (approximate)**
 - **Educational Level**
 - Lower Secondary Education (3rd Cycle)
 - Upper Secondary Education
 - Other
 - **What measures were taken to attract underrepresented audiences to this type of event, such as students from disadvantaged communities and/or minorities, and to ensure diversity in gender, age, and socioeconomic background within the group?**
 - **Was this goal achieved? To what extent?**
(Describe the type of audience and the diversity in terms of gender, age, and socioeconomic background.)
-

Scientists

(Description optional)

- **Number of Scientists Involved**
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3 or more

- **Scientific Area of the Scientists**
- **Was gender equality achieved among scientists and other experts?**
- **Please rate the following statements based on your level of agreement:**
 - The scientist(s) adapted their language to the age/knowledge level of the students.
 - The scientist(s) encouraged student participation.
 - The scientist(s) showed interest in the students' questions/opinions.

Effect of the Session on Participants

To answer the following questions: record the number of positive responses to the questions asked at the end of the debate, out of the total number of participants.

(For example, assuming 16 students participated:

Who knew that the European Commission had defined 5 missions? 9/16

Who had previously participated in a debate? 5/16

Who had thought about the topic under discussion before? 14/16

Etc.)

- **Who knew that the European Commission had defined 5 missions?**
- **Who had previously participated in a debate?**
- **Who had thought about the topic under discussion before?**
- **Which missions have scientists working in Portugal? (Indicate the response for each mission.)**

- **During the session, students were:**
 - Bored
 - Distracted
 - Attentive
 - Enthusiastic
 - Participative
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact/change in the participants? What changed?**

(For example, students may have spoken to a scientist for the first time, learned something new, discovered a scientific career path, or formed an opinion on a new topic...)

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

- **Evidence of Change**

(Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the changes identified. You may also add photographs or other evidence of the activity's impact.)

Note: If you want to include photographs, make sure to ask for permission to photograph, ensure the images do not show faces (photograph from behind), and that no students are recognizable.

- **Other observations/comments to help us assess the session's impact on participants (and on scientists)**
- **Photographs**

Participatory Debates – Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us better understand the audience that participated in this debate on Horizon Europe missions through statistical indicators.

The answers are personal, so please respond based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to respond or exit the survey at any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the survey will take no more than 5 minutes, and your contributions will be highly valuable to improve both your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized under the EU-EMBRACES project.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact:

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

Consent

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the information above and that you are voluntarily participating.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Share your impressions about this debate

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the session** (from 1 not satisfied to 5 completely satisfied)
- **What did you enjoy the most?**
- **What did you dislike or think could be improved?**
- **Do you feel that your opinion was important in the conclusions of the debate?**
 - Yes
 - Maybe, it's hard to tell
 - I don't feel that my opinion was considered
 - I did not have the opportunity to share my opinion
 - I had the opportunity to share my opinion, but I chose not to
 - Other...
- **I didn't know, but in this session I learned that...**

Help us better understand the audience that participated in these debates through statistical indicators

- **School Year**
 - 7th grade
 - 8th grade
 - 9th grade
 - 10th grade
 - 11th grade
 - 12th grade
- **School**
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other...
- **Your Mother's Education Level**
 - No education
 - Basic education

- Secondary education
 - Higher education
 - Other...
- **Was this the first time you directly interacted with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know
- **Did anything surprise you during this interaction? If yes, what?**
- **Do you think you could become a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know
- **Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside of school)?**
 - No, never
 - Yes, occasionally
 - Yes, regularly

Participatory Debates (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perceptions of the Participatory Debates under the EU-EMBRACES project.

The responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this questionnaire is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or exit the survey at any point.

Your responses will always remain confidential.

The answers will be submitted to a link in GoogleForms accessible only to the project's researchers. GoogleForms does not require registration or collect identifying data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether or not you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions about the study or procedures, you can contact us at any time via **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

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ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information above.
 - You are voluntarily participating.
 - You are 18 years or older.
 - I Agree
 - I Do Not Agree (exit survey)
-

- **Age:**
 - Under 35 years
 - 35–44 years
 - 45–54 years
 - 55–64 years
 - Over 65 years
- **Gender:**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other...
- **Field of Scientific Activity:**
 - Exact Sciences
 - Natural Sciences
 - Engineering and Technology
 - Medical and Health Sciences
 - Agricultural Sciences
 - Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other...
- **Professional Category:**
 - Master's Student
 - PhD Student

- Postdoctoral Researcher with a Fellowship or Fixed-Term Contract
- Career Researcher or Lecturer
- Other...

- **Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct interaction with the public)?**
 - No, it was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2–4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate regularly (5 or more times per year)
- **How would you describe the students with whom you interacted in this session?**
- **Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If yes, please explain how.**
- **From the perspective of your participation, highlight the positive aspects you would emphasize.**
- **From the perspective of your participation, highlight challenges you encountered or aspects that could be improved.**
- **Other observations/comments:**

9.4 Social inclusion through science and technology

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods – Activity Form (Organizers)

This form is designed to gather information about the activities and workshops conducted in neighborhoods as part of the "Social Inclusion through Science" program. One form should be completed for each event/activity.

The form should be filled out by the entity responsible for the activity, ideally by someone directly involved in its implementation. The fields in the form pertain to the activity, the participants, the impact of the activity on participants, and the scientists involved. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if it is not possible to fill out all fields.

Filling out the form does not require much time. We thank you in advance for your collaboration.

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The Activity

- **Activity Title**
 - **Date** (*Month, day, year*)
 - **Location**
 - **Duration**
 - **Type of Activity**
 - **Organizing Entity**
 - **Horizon Europe Mission addressed in the session (if applicable)**
 - Beating Cancer
 - Fighting Climate Change
 - Building the Cities of the Future
 - Ensuring Soil and Food Health
 - Protecting the Oceans
 - Not applicable
 - **Did you receive support from any neighborhood structure or person/entity working in the neighborhood?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **If yes, can you specify the type of entity or structure that provided support?**
 - **Was it important for the success of the event?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not applicable
-

Participants

- **Number of Participants (approximate)**
- **Age Range of Participants**
- **Context(s) of Participants** (*e.g., school, families, migrant community, adults, children, etc.*)
- **Compared to other activities organized, was it more difficult to attract participants?**

- Yes
- No

Scientists

- **Number of Scientists Involved**
- **Scientific Areas of the Scientists**
- **Compared to other activities organized, was it more difficult to recruit scientists?**
 - Yes
 - No

Impact of the Activity on Participants

- **Participants' Satisfaction with the Activity** (*Where 1 means Very Dissatisfied and 5 means Very Satisfied*)
- **How was participants' satisfaction assessed?**
 - Observation
 - Surveys
 - Written Comments
 - Oral Comments
 - Dotmocracy
 - Post-it Wall
 - Questions with raised-hand votes
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact or change on the participants? What changed?** (*For example:*
 - *Participants who had never been exposed to science before, spoke with a scientist for the first time, learned that being a scientist is a viable career in Portugal, or discovered new aspects of science.*
 - *Scientists who had never interacted with the public before...*

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.)
- **Evidence of Change**

(Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the change observed. You may also add photos of the event or other evidence of the activity's impact, such as dotmocracy, post-it wall, etc.)
- **Photographs**

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods - Satisfaction Survey (Participants)

The following questions aim to evaluate your perception of this event and help us better understand the audience that joined us through statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Completing this questionnaire should not take more than 5 minutes. Participation is voluntary, and you may choose not to answer or leave the survey at any time. Your answers will be extremely helpful in improving your experience, as well as that of other participants, in future activities. We guarantee that your responses will always remain confidential.

This survey is part of the EU-EMBRACES project funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact

If you have any questions about the study or procedures at any time, you can contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

Consent

By agreeing, you indicate that you have read the above information and are participating voluntarily.

I agree

I do not agree

Share your impressions with us!

- **Rate your level of satisfaction with the event from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
- **What did you like the most?**
- **What could be improved?**
- **What did you learn that you did not know before?**
- **Was there anything that surprised you?**

Now, help us learn more about the audience that joined us for this event by providing some information about yourself.

Age

- Under 15 years old
- 15–24 years old
- 25–34 years old
- 35–44 years old
- 45–54 years old
- 55–64 years old
- 65 years or older

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other

Postal Code (if living outside Portugal, you can indicate the country)

Level of Education

- Primary education - 1st cycle
- Primary education - 2nd cycle
- Primary education - 3rd cycle
- Secondary education
- Post-secondary education
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Other

Employment Status

- Student
- Employed
- Unemployed
- Homemaker

- Retired
- Other

Your mother's level of education

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education
- Other

Was this your first time interacting with a scientist?

- Yes
- No

Do you often participate in science events or festivals?

- I had never participated before
- Yes, occasionally
- Yes, frequently

What is your connection to science?

- I have no direct connection to science
- I have friends or family members who are scientists
- I have training in a scientific field
- I work or have worked in science
- Other

Activities and Workshops in Neighborhoods – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perceptions of this event. Responses are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 3 minutes.

Participation is voluntary. You may choose not to complete it or abandon it at any time.

Your responses will always remain confidential. They will be submitted through a Google Forms link, which is accessible only to the project researchers. Google Forms

does not require registration or collect identifying data, such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

If you have any questions about the study or its procedures, you may contact us at sci@itqb.unl.pt.

This event is part of the European Researchers' Night 2024, organized within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent form for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you indicate that:

- You have read the information provided above;
- You are participating voluntarily;
- You are 18 years of age or older.

*

I Agree

I Do Not Agree (exit survey)

Event or Activity Title / Date / Organization / Location

Age

- Under 35 years old
- 35–44 years old
- 45–54 years old
- 55–64 years old
- Over 65 years old

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to answer
- Other

Scientific Field

- Exact Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Other

Professional Category / Relationship with Science

- Master's Student
- PhD Student
- Postdoctoral Researcher with a Fellowship or Fixed-term Contract
- Career Researcher or Lecturer
- Other

Have you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct interaction with the public)?

- No, this was my first time
- Yes, I occasionally participate
- Yes, I regularly participate (2–4 times per year)
- Yes, I frequently participate (5 or more times per year)

How would you describe the people you interacted with during this activity?

Do you feel that your participation in this activity was rewarding? If yes, in what way?

From the perspective of your participation, highlight the positive aspects of this activity.

From the perspective of your participation, mention the challenges you faced or aspects that could be improved.

Was there anything that surprised you about the target audience?

Additional Comments

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools – Session Form (Teachers)

This form is intended to collect information about the "Meet the Scientists" sessions organized as part of the European Researchers' Night in 2024 and 2025. A separate form should be completed for each session.

The form is to be completed by the teacher who attended the session. It includes fields related to the activity, the scientists, the participants, and the impact of the activity on the participants. It may be necessary to plan the collection of this information in advance. Please submit the form with the available information, even if some fields cannot be completed.

Filling out this form does not take much time. Thank you in advance for your cooperation.

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-
- **Location of the activity**
 - **Session topic**
 - **Horizon Europe mission addressed in the session (if applicable):**
 - Beating cancer
 - Combating climate change
 - Building the cities of the future
 - Ensuring soil health and food security
 - Protecting the oceans
 - Not applicable
 - **Duration of the session**
 - **Session description**

Briefly explain the nature of the session, mentioning the socioeconomic context of the school and any established (or absent) habits of interaction with scientists.

Describe the conditions that influenced the interaction, either facilitating or hindering it. (For example, detail the venue, available space, and materials used, such as computers or laboratory equipment.)

Participants

- **Approximate number of students**
- **Educational level:**
 - Primary School (1st cycle)
 - Primary School (2nd cycle)
 - Primary School (3rd cycle)
 - Secondary School
 - Other

Scientists

- **Number of scientists involved:**
- **Scientific field(s) of the scientist(s)**
- **Rate the following statements based on your level of agreement:**
(*Agree / Neither agree nor disagree / Disagree / Not applicable*)
 - The scientist(s) successfully adapted their communication to the students' age/knowledge level.
 - The scientist(s) made an effort to encourage student participation.
 - The scientist(s) demonstrated interest in the students' questions and opinions.

Effect of the session on participants

- During the session, the students were:
 - Bored
 - Distracted
 - Attentive
 - Enthusiastic
 - Engaged
 - Other...
- **Was it possible to identify any impact or change in the participants? If so, what changed?**
(*For example: Some students spoke with a scientist for the first time, learned*

something new, discovered a scientific career, or formed an opinion on a new topic.)

Note: It is not always possible to provoke or identify changes.

- **Evidence of change**

Include comments, testimonials, or observations that demonstrate the change observed.

You may also attach photographs or other materials that highlight the impact of the activity.

Note: If including photographs, ensure you have permission to take them.

Photographs should not include identifiable faces (e.g., taken from behind) or any recognizable details of students.

- **Additional observations/comments**

Share any other comments that may help us assess the impact of the session on the participants (and the scientists).

- **Photographs**

Activities and Workshops in TEIP Schools – Survey (Students)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate your perception of this session and help us better understand the audience who participated in this event through statistical indicators.

Your responses are personal, so please answer based on your own experience. Participation is voluntary, and you can choose not to answer or exit the survey at any time. Your responses will always remain confidential. Completing the questionnaire will take no more than 5 minutes, and your input is highly valuable to improving your experience and that of other participants in future activities.

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Contact

If you have any questions about the study or its procedures, you can contact us at any time at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

Consent

By agreeing, you confirm that you have read the above information and that you are participating voluntarily.

- **I agree**
 - **I do not agree**
-

Share your impressions of this session.

- **:Rate your level of satisfaction with the session from 1 (not satisfied at all) to 5 (completely satisfied).**
 - **What did you like the most?**
 - **What do you think could be improved?**
 - **Something I didn't know but learned during this session...**
-

Help us better understand the audience who joined this event through statistical indicators.

- **Grade**
 - 7th grade
 - 8th grade
 - 9th grade
 - 10th grade
 - 11th grade
 - 12th grade
- **School**
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
 - Other...
- **Your mother's level of education**
 - No formal education

- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education
- Other...
- **Was this your first time interacting directly with a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I'm not sure
- **Was there anything that surprised you about this interaction? What?**
- **Do you think you could become a scientist?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - I'm not sure
- **Have you participated in other science-related activities (outside school)?**
 - No, never
 - Yes, sometimes
 - Yes, regularly

Activities and Workshops in Schools – Survey (Scientists)

This questionnaire aims to evaluate scientists' perception of the "Meet the Scientist" event within the scope of the EU-EMBRACES project.

The answers are personal.

Completing this questionnaire should take no more than 5 minutes.

Participation in this survey is voluntary. You may choose not to participate in this survey or leave it at any point.

Your responses will always be confidential.

The answers will be sent to a link on Google Forms, which only the project researchers have access to. Google Forms does not require registration or collect identifying data such as IP addresses. No one will be able to identify your identity or know whether you participated in the survey.

CONTACT

If you have any questions at any time regarding the study or the procedures, you can contact us at **sci@itqb.unl.pt**.

The EU-EMBRACES project is funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the positions of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

ELECTRONIC CONSENT:

Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent for your records. By clicking "I Agree," you confirm that:

- You have read the above information.
 - You are participating voluntarily.
 - You are 18 years of age or older.
 - **I agree**
 - **I do not agree (exit survey)**
-

- **Age**
 - Under 35 years
 - 35-44 years
 - 45-54 years
 - 55-64 years
 - Over 65 years
- **Gender**
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to respond
 - Other...
- **Field of Scientific Activity**
 - Exact Sciences
 - Natural Sciences
 - Engineering and Technology
 - Medical and Health Sciences
 - Agricultural Sciences
 - Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other...
- **Professional Category**
 - Master's Student
 - Doctoral Student

- Doctorate holder with grant or fixed-term contract
 - Career Researcher or Professor
 - Other...
- **Had you previously participated in science communication activities of this type (direct contact with the public)?**
 - No, it was my first time
 - Yes, I participate occasionally
 - Yes, I participate regularly (2-4 times per year)
 - Yes, I participate frequently (5 or more times per year)
- **Type of participation in the session:**
 - Online
 - In-person
- **How would you describe the students you interacted with during this session?**
- **Do you feel your participation in this session was rewarding for you? If so, in what way?**
- **From your perspective, what positive aspects would you highlight from your participation?**
- **From your perspective, what challenges did you encounter or aspects that could be improved?**
- **Was there anything that surprised you regarding the target audience?**
- **Other observations/comments**